

DEVELOPMENT OF DRILLING TECHNOLOGY WITH HYDRAULIC MOTORS IN SALT BLOOD CONDITIONS.

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Abstract: *Improving the efficiency of deep wells and fairways in oilfields with salt rock deposits by developing and implementing drilling techniques and technologies through hydraulic drilling motors (HDM).*

An overview of the works on the improvement of the turbine drilling method, the constructions and characteristics of hydraulic well engines are presented. The works of researchers such as Abiyan XL, Ageev AI, Astafyev GK, Astafyev PI, Bagirov RE are devoted to solving the problems of optimizing the drilling mode of hydrodynamic pumps, determining their stable operation zones and operational reliability. ., Baldenko DF, Baldenko FD, Balitsky VP, Barshay GS, Bikchurin TN, Bobrov MG, Budyansky VS, Bulatov KV, Bulakh GI, Gelfgat Ya.A., Gnoevyx AN, Ya.A., Gnoevyx AN, Grievman P., N. Grievman, N. Grieve. Kach ND, Ilsky AL, Ioannesyan RA, Ioanesyan Yu.R., Korotaev Yu.A., Kochnev AM, Kravets SG, Krutik EN, Kuzin BV, Kulyabin GA, Kurumov LS, Litvyak VA, Lyubimov, GAG, Lyubimov, GAG , Malyshev DG, Meliya VA, Moiseenko VM, Nikitin GM, Nikomarov SS, Orlov AV, Pogarsky AA, Popko VV, Potapov Yu.F., Simonyants LE, Simonyants SL, Sultanov BZ, Shukovsky TP, Shukovsky PZVP, Eskin MG and others. The analysis and generalization of the results of scientific research made it possible to determine the modern technical and technological requirements for the constructions and characteristics of hydraulic engines used in drilling deep oil and gas wells in complex geological conditions. the purpose and tasks of the dissertation work.

It was decided to implement the development of an efficient technology of drilling deep wells with hydraulic well engines on the example of the Pripyat deep oil fields of the Republic of Belarus. Difficult mine-geological conditions for the construction of wells in these deposits are associated with the presence of two autonomous salt layers on the site, which separate terrigenous, carbonate and volcanogenic structures, and the division of the site into five lithological complexes of different ages: subsalt (terrigenous and carbonate), lower saline r, inter-salt, high-salt and post-salt , a sharp difference in their lithological composition, an intense manifestation of salt-dome tectonics and a significant difference in reservoir pressure across stratigraphic complexes and horizons. The need to open above and below horizons with inconsistent drilling conditions requires the use of heavy and multi-column well structures, as well as the use of different types of drilling fluid. Such in the circumstances drilling process most of the time the well of the walls stability break with it gets complicated .

Pripyat groove mines complicated mine-geological conditions deep wells and drilling ways hydraulic the well engines with drilling technological process to improve complex the approach set gave , this the following features account take need :

- salty deposits from 500 - 800 to 3500 - 4500 m has been in the depths appear will be , therefore for them drilling high in density drilling at low costs of fluids done increase need _

- salt rock mines of drilling PDM worker couples of rotors to work negative effect showing salt with saturated drilling liquids using done increase need _
- low layer pressure conditions fertile horizons to open , to surface coming to losses against fight traditional measures apply with one in line , stuck stay new efficient methods work exit Demand does ;
- hard carbonated in layers small diameter of the sides open the ends drilling for embedded with diamonds from bits use the well of the driver moment increase Demand does ;
- main and addition mines efficient drilling which provides integrated technology work exit need _

This current problems solution in doing scientific and methodical approach the following to the rules based on Bit and hydraulic of pads work learning them work exit about reliable information analysis do , hydraulic pads repair during check results , new the wells drilling for Belorusneft PO RUE electronic data bases analysis to do based on done increase need _ Information again of work statistics methods used without and sides . _ Field information analysis to do and generalization as a result from salt next and salted in mines , between salts and to salt has been of mines carbonate and terrigenous in the rocks genders drilling for the most effective bit types determination need _ From this besides , salt rock _ mines drilling to the conditions suitable coming , eng high fertility and energy features have has been the most good DHM types determination need _

PDM properties theoretical and machine tool studies the field tests results with confirmation need _ Lice and hydraulic of engines work analysis to do and generalization results belongs to guidelines in the form of Created deep wells and sides _ drilling according to technological recommendations Create for use need - RUE PO Belorusneft of the enterprise standards .

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